

LEADERSHIP RESPONSE TO SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF ARMED BANDITRY IN ZAMFARA STATE, NORTHWEST NIGERIA FROM 2019-2024

In Bako Suleiman¹, Brig. Gen. OA Ogunleye PhD², Onah Otumala Peter PhD² & David Markus Shekwolo PhD³

¹Directorate of Army Physical Training, Muhammadu Buhari Cantonment, Giri, Abuja.

²Department of History and War Studies, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna

³Department of Psychology, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna

Email: sulgolman77@gmail.com Phone Number: 08032204332

ABSTRACT

Armed banditry has become a major threat to socio-economic development in Zamfara State, Northwest Nigeria. Based on this situation, this study examined the socio-economic, educational, health, and psychological impacts of armed banditry across selected LGAs. It also assessed government and NGO's responses, identified critical drivers of banditry, and evaluated community-preferred strategies for addressing the crisis. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, and structured questionnaires were administered to 414 respondents in Tsafe, Zurmi, and Maru LGAs. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and presented in frequencies and percentages. Findings showed severe consequences across all sectors. Most respondents reported disruption of farming activities (91.3%), livestock losses (96.61%), reduced agricultural output (98.07%), and loss of livelihood (81.16%). Social effects included overcrowded IDP camps (97.82%), family separation (96.13%), and increased disease and malnutrition (93.24%). Education was equally affected, with displacement of children (99.03%), frequent school closures (76.5%), and heightened child labour and early marriage (96.62%). Healthcare services declined due to destruction of facilities (68.4%), displacement of workers (88.2%), and restricted medical access (88.4%). Psychological distress was widespread, including PTSD (93.23%) and depression (97.10%). Poverty (84.54%) emerged as the most critical driver of banditry, followed by unemployment (41.54%) and weak governance (40.05%). Preferred strategies included enhanced security measures (86.82%), economic support programmes (41.69%), and community engagement (37.22%). Overall, armed banditry imposes multidimensional disruptions requiring urgent multi sectorial action. Strengthening security structures, expanding poverty-reduction and employment initiatives, improving social services, and promoting community-driven peace building are essential for restoring long-term stability and resilience in affected communities.

Keywords: Leadership response, Socio-economic and Armed banditry

Introduction

Armed banditry has become one of the most pressing threats to Nigeria's socio-economic stability, particularly in the Northern and central regions where communities depend heavily on agriculture, trade, and local economic networks for survival (Abdulfatai, 2021; Abdullahi & Mukhtar, 2022). This phenomenon marked by kidnapping, robbery, cattle rustling, village raids, and destruction of property has evolved from isolated criminal acts into a systemic crisis that undermines national security, disrupts livelihoods, and weakens the fabric of rural society (Akindoyin & Akuche, 2023). States such as Zamfara, Katsina, and Kaduna have borne the heaviest burden. Once vibrant agricultural belts, they now struggle with mass displacement as farmers flee their communities, leaving farmlands uncultivated and worsening Nigeria's food insecurity and poverty indicators (Mahmoud et al., 2022; Rjoub et al., 2021; Abdullahi et al., 2022).

The situation in Zamfara State widely regarded as the epicenter of banditry in Nigeria illustrates the magnitude of the crisis. The rural LGAs of Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe have endured significant levels of violence over the past decade, each experiencing unique but interconnected patterns of attack that reveal how deeply the phenomenon has penetrated local governance systems and daily life of the people. In Maru LGA, banditry has escalated due to its forested terrain and proximity to major escape routes linking Zamfara with Katsina and Niger States. Many communities, such as Dansadau and Bindin, have repeatedly faced cattle rustling, abductions, and arson attacks that destroy homes and farmlands. These attacks have triggered waves of internal displacement, forcing residents to abandon fertile farmlands that once contributed substantially to the area's grain production. Local leaders, overwhelmed and under-resourced, struggle to coordinate security responses or negotiate safe passage for trapped residents. As villagers recount nights spent hiding in nearby bushes, it becomes clear that the human toll in Maru extends far beyond material losses it includes deep-seated trauma and a collapse of community trust.

Zurmi LGA, located near the Nigeria–Niger Republic border, presents another dimension of the crisis. Its geographical position makes it a transit corridor for illicit arms, smuggling operations, and cross-border bandit movements. Communities such as Boko, Yan Buki, and Kwashabawa have experienced persistent attacks, often carried out by heavily armed groups who take advantage of the porous border to evade Nigerian security forces. The bandit networks operating in Zurmi have also disrupted one of the LGA's strongest economic activities which is livestock trading. Cattle markets once bustling with buyers from across the region now operate under constant threat, while traders live with the fear of abduction on their way to and from market routes. Households that depended on livestock as their primary source of income have been plunged into poverty, their herds stolen or scattered. Zurmi's residents often describe living in a state of perpetual uncertainty, unsure whether their daily routines will be interrupted by gunfire, mass abductions, or forced displacement.

The story is similarly troubling in Tsafe LGA, a region that has become a hotspot for both roadside kidnappings and large-scale village raids. Positioned along strategic road networks that link Zamfara to Katsina and Kaduna, Tsafe has witnessed a surge in attacks that primarily target travelers, traders, and farming communities. Villages such as Yandoto, Keta, and Mada have repeatedly been raided sometimes in broad daylight resulting in deaths, destruction of property, and the disintegration of local economies. Many families in Tsafe recount losing loved ones, livestock, and farmlands within short periods, leaving them dependent on humanitarian support and overstretched government relief services. School attendance has also dropped drastically as parents keep children at home for fear of mass kidnapping incidents. The persistent insecurity has weakened traditional leadership structures and increased mistrust between residents and the government, with many questioning the state's capacity to protect them.

These local experiences reflect broader trends across West Africa, where armed banditry is often rooted in poverty, youth unemployment, weak governance, and competition over dwindling natural resources. The consequences ripple outward, triggering displacement, food insecurity, and economic decline across entire regions. Governments and community leaders have responded through a mix of strategies community defense groups, national security operations, regional security coalitions, and international support efforts. However, decades of research and real-time experiences reveal that the most effective approaches are those that integrate security with livelihoods, governance reforms, and cross-border collaboration to address underlying causes rather than just symptoms (Abdullahi et al., 2022).

Beyond the economic fallout, the social costs of armed banditry are profound and far-reaching. Education systems have been severely disrupted, especially in states like Zamfara where schools have become deliberate

targets for mass abductions. These attacks have frightened students, teachers, and parents, shrinking school enrollment, particularly for girls, who already face significant educational barriers (Oladoyin et al., 2024). Similarly, healthcare delivery has been compromised. Health workers avoid volatile communities, facilities are attacked or abandoned, and displaced populations put enormous pressure on remaining services (Okwuwada, 2023). These conditions accelerate preventable diseases, maternal health risks, and malnutrition in affected areas. Businesses and investors also avoid conflict zones, deepening cycles of underdevelopment while skilled individuals migrate to safer regions in search of stability and opportunity (Okwuwada, 2023; Ishola et al., 2024).

In this complex landscape, leadership emerges as a decisive factor in shaping outcomes. Strong and accountable leadership at the federal, state, and local levels has the potential to drive security reforms, promote community engagement, and support long-term conflict resolution efforts (Ojewale, 2024; Ugbomah et al., 2022). However, where leadership fails—whether through poor governance, corruption, lack of political will, or failure to respond promptly—the crisis intensifies (Ojewale, 2024). Communities in Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe repeatedly express frustration over delayed security responses, inadequate protection, and weak coordination among security actors. Effective leadership would therefore require not only improving security infrastructure but also enhancing trust, transparency, and collaboration with local communities (Odalonu, 2022).

Furthermore, addressing the root causes of banditry demands leadership that invests in economic empowerment, youth engagement, education, and healthcare (Omitola et al., 2021; Odalonu & Egbogu, 2023). Holistic approaches that create job opportunities, support local agriculture, improve access to quality schooling, and strengthen local governance systems can help weaken the appeal of criminal networks. As communities often emphasize, peace cannot be sustained by military operations alone, it requires leadership that listens, empathizes, and responds effectively to the realities on the ground.

This study therefore examines the intersection of leadership and armed banditry with the aim of proposing actionable strategies for achieving sustainable peace, human security, and socio-economic development in Nigeria (Iregbenu & Uzonwanne, 2015).

[www.https://gmijp-edu.com](https://gmijp-edu.com)

Statement of the Problem

Armed banditry in Zamfara State, Northwest Nigeria, has escalated into a major security and developmental crisis, marked by mass killings, kidnappings, displacement, and destruction of livelihoods. The violence has devastated agriculture, disrupted trade, increased poverty, and eroded public trust in governance. Despite various leadership interventions ranging from military operations and peace negotiations to community engagement responses have often been fragmented, reactive, and short-lived, failing to address underlying drivers such as rural poverty, youth unemployment, and weak state presence. This has allowed bandit groups to adapt and persist, deepening the socio-economic impact. Understanding and evaluating leadership responses is crucial to formulating sustainable strategies that combine security, socio-economic development, and governance reforms to restore peace and resilience in Zamfara State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What are the socio-economic impacts of armed banditry in Nigeria?
- ii. How has leadership at various levels responded to the challenge of armed banditry?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the role of leadership in addressing the socio-economic impact of armed banditry in Zamfara State, Northwest Nigeria, with a focus on evaluating the effectiveness of existing leadership strategies and identifying new approaches to mitigate the problem and foster sustainable development in affected regions. However, the objectives of the study are to

- i. Examine the socio-economic impacts of armed banditry in Nigeria.
- ii. Assess the responses of leadership at various levels to the challenge of armed banditry.
- iii. Identify leadership strategies and best practices that have been effective in mitigating the impact of armed banditry.
- iv. Recommend ways leadership can be improved to enhance socio-economic development in areas affected by armed banditry.

Method

This section outlines the research method employed to achieve the study's objectives and answer the research questions. It provides a detailed description of the research design, data collection methods, and analytical techniques adopted for a robust analysis, ensuring a systematic and replicable approach. The chosen method aligns with the theoretical framework and addresses the identified gaps in the literature review, facilitating a robust investigation of the research problem.

The section is organized into research design, population and sample selection, data collection (instruments), procedures, and methods of analysis. Additionally, ethical considerations and limitations of the method are discussed to ensure transparency and integrity in the research process.

Research Design

The research design adopted for this study was a mixed-method approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative methods. This design was chosen to provide a comprehensive understanding of the role of leadership in addressing the impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria. The quantitative aspect involved the use of structured Google form questionnaires to collect numerical data, while the qualitative aspect involved interviews and focus groups to gather in-depth insights.

Population

The study was conducted in the regions of Nigeria most affected by armed banditry, including Maru LGA, Zurmi LGA and Tsarfe LGA. These areas have been chosen due to their high incidence of banditry and significant impact on socio-economic activities. The total population of the area is 1,078, 608 while the study

includes local community members, government officials, security personnel, and representatives from non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The following are the estimated population

ISSN: 2971-7769 Vol: 3, Number: 3, Date: 05/01/2026

Population size of Maru LGA= 316,600

Population size of Zurmi LGA = 496,000

Population size of Tsafe LGA = 266,008

Total population of the three LGA's = 1,078,608

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

A combination of purposive and simple random sampling techniques was employed. Purposive sampling was used to select key informants, such as community leaders and government officials, who have direct experience and knowledge of the issue. Simple random sampling technique was used to select a representative sample of community members. The sample size was determined based on the population of each study area, aiming for a total of approximately 400 participants to ensure statistical validity.

Using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1078608}{1+108608 \times (0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 399.8517$$
$$= 400$$

10% drop out = 40

$$400+40 = 440$$

GMIJP, NSUK
www.https://gmijp-edu.com

Methods of Data Collection

Primary data was collected through structured Google form questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, and focus group discussions. The questionnaires were designed to gather quantitative data on the socio-economic impact of banditry, while the interviews and focus groups provided qualitative insights into the leadership responses and strategies.

Questionnaires: Distributed to community members to collect data on their experiences and the socio-economic impact of banditry.

Interviews: Conducted with government officials, security personnel, and NGO representatives to understand leadership responses.

Focus Groups: Held with community leaders and members to discuss the effectiveness of various strategies and gather recommendations.

Secondary data was gathered from existing literature, government reports, NGO publications, and academic studies. This data provided contextual background and support the primary data collected.

Validity and Reliability

To ensure reliability and validity, the study employed triangulation by using multiple data sources and methods. The questionnaire was pre-tested to refine questions for clarity and accuracy. Consistency in data collection procedures was maintained, and data analysis methods were rigorously applied to ensure robust and credible results.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are paramount in this study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they are aware of the study's purpose and their right to withdraw at any time. Confidentiality and anonymity was maintained throughout the research process. Additionally, the study adhered to ethical guidelines for conducting research in conflict-affected areas, including sensitivity to the trauma experienced by participants.

Methods of Data Analysis

Data analysis involved both qualitative and quantitative methods. Quantitative data from the questionnaires was analyzed using statistical techniques, including descriptive statistics and regression analysis, to identify patterns and relationships. Qualitative data from interviews and focus groups was analyzed using thematic analysis to identify key themes and insights.

Results

[www.https://gmijp-edu.com](https://gmijp-edu.com)

This section aims to translate raw data into meaningful insights by systematically presenting and analyzing the information gathered through various research methods. The presentation of data is organized to highlight key findings and trends, using descriptive statistics, visual aids such as charts and graphs, and qualitative analysis where applicable.

Presentation and Analysis of Data

The data collection process yielded comprehensive quantitative and qualitative data from various respondents in the regions affected by armed banditry in Nigeria. A total of 414 Google form questionnaires were filled online. Additionally, 30 semi-structured interviews were conducted with government officials, security personnel, and NGO representatives.

Table 1: Gender Distribution of Respondents

ISSN: 2971-7760, Vol: 3, Number: 3, Date: 05/01/2026

	N	Percentage (%)
Male	54	13
Female	360	87
Total	414	100

The socio-demographic characteristics of respondents are presented in Tables 1. The gender distribution shows that majority of the participants were female, with 360 females (87%) compared to 54 males (13%), indicating that females were more accessible or more willing to participate in the study.

Table 2: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age (years)	N	Percentage (%)
20-30	61	14.8
31-40	126	30.5
41-50	183	44.1
51 and above	44	10.6
Total	414	100

The age distribution reveals that the largest age group was 41–50 years (44.1%), followed by those aged 31–40 years (30.5%), suggesting that most respondents were mature adults who likely engaged in economic activities affected by armed banditry.

Table 3: Educational Level Distribution of Respondents

Education level	n	Percentage (%)
No formal education	41	9.9
Primary education	24	5.8
Secondary education	82	19.8
Tertiary education	267	64.4
Total	414	100

Educational attainment (Table 3) indicates that a majority, 267 respondents (64.4%), had tertiary education, while only 41 (9.9%) had no formal education. This shows that respondents possess reasonable literacy levels to provide valid information.

Table 4: Occupational Distribution of Respondents

Occupation	n	Percentage (%)
Farmer	93	22.5
Trader	49	11.8
Civil Servant	176	42.5
Unemployed	26	6.2

Occupational data (Table 4) show that civil servants constituted the largest group (42.5%), followed by farmers (22.5%) and traders (11.8%).

Table 5: Regions of the Respondents

Region	N	Percentage (%)
Tsafe	140	33.8
Zurmi	113	27.4
Maru	70	16.9
Total	414	100

Table 5 shows that respondents were drawn mainly from Tsafe (33.8%), Zurmi (27.4%), and Maru (16.9%).

Table 6: Agricultural Activities Affected Armed Banditry

Agricultural Activities	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Disruption of Farming activities	Farming activities affected	378	91.3
	Farming activities not affected	36	8.70
	Total	414	100
Economic losses	Economic losses	365	88.16
	Economic not lost	49	11.84
	Total	414	100
Loss of Livestock	Livestock lost	400	96.61
	Livestock not lost	14	3.39
	Total	414	100
Farmers Displacement	Displaced	405	97.83
	Not Displaced	9	2.17
	Total	414	100
Reduced Agricultural output	Reduced	406	98.07
	Not reduced	8	1.93
	Total	414	100

Table.6 highlights the severe agricultural and economic impact of armed banditry, with 91.3% reporting disruption of farming activities, 88.16% reporting economic losses, 96.61% reporting livestock losses, 97.83% reporting displacement, and 98.07% reporting reduced agricultural output. These figures underscore the widespread destructive effect of banditry on rural livelihoods.

Table 7 Effects of Armed Banditry on Agricultural Activities

Agricultural Activities	N	Percentage (%)
Reduced productivity	287	69.3
Loss of livestock	46	11.1
Destruction of crops	55	13.4
Others	26	6.3
Total	414	100

Table 7 shows that reduction in agricultural productivity is the most common effect of banditry, reported by 287 respondents (69.3%). Other notable impacts include destruction of crops (13.4%) and loss of livestock (11.1%), while 6.3% cited additional effects. This indicates severe disruption of food production systems.

Table.8: Armed Banditry’s Impact on Household Income

Armed Banditry Impact	Responses	n	Percentage (%)
Livelihood	Livelihood lost	336	81.16
	Livelihood not lost	78	18.84
	Total	414	100
Agricultural Productivity	Agricultural Productivity reduced	376	90.82
	Agricultural Productivity not reduced	36	8.18
	Total	414	100
Assets	Assets lost	341	82.36
	Assets not lost	73	17.64
	Total	414	100
Displacement and Migration	People are displaced and migrate	317	76.57
	People are displaced and migrate	97	23.43
	Total	414	100
Businesses	Impact on businesses	320	77.29
	No Impact on businesses	94	22.71
	Total	414	100

Table 8 highlights the significant consequences on household income. A large proportion (81.16%) reported loss of livelihood, while 90.82% indicated reduction in agricultural productivity. Loss of household assets was also high at 82.36%, and 76.57% reported displacement and migration. Additionally, 77.29% noted negative impacts on business activities, showing that banditry undermines economic stability at both household and community levels.

Table 9: Effects of Disruptions in Local Markets Due to Banditry

What are the disruptions in local markets due to banditry?	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Rural Economies	Rural Economies collapsed	381	92.03
	Rural Economies have not collapsed	33	7.97
	Total	414	100
Inflation and Food Supply	Shortages in inflation and food	413	99.75
	No Shortages in inflation and food	1	0.25
	Total	414	100
Livelihoods	Livelihood lost	376	90.82
	Livelihood not lost	38	9.18
	Total	414	100
Agricultural Productivity	Agricultural Productivity decline	356	85.99
	Agricultural Productivity not declined	58	14.01
	Total	414	100
Investor and Buyer Confidence	Reduced	337	81.40
	Not reduced	77	18.60
	Total	414	100

Table 9 further demonstrates the collapse of local markets. Rural economies were reported to have collapsed by 92.03% of respondents, while 99.75% observed inflation and food shortages. Loss of livelihoods (90.82%), decline in agricultural productivity (85.99%), and reduced investor/buyer confidence (81.40%) all point to widespread economic deterioration.

Table 10: Frequency of the Bandit Disruptions

If yes, how often do these disruptions occur?	Responses	n	Percentage (%)
Attacks on Villages	Regular	307	74.20
	Not regular	107	25.80
	Total	414	100
Surge in Violence	Seasonal	381	92.02
	Not seasonal	33	7.98
	Total	414	100
Threat to Farming Cycles	Constant	326	78.74
	Not constant	88	21.26

	Total	414	100
School Closures	Re-occurring	345	83.33
	Not re-occurring	69	16.67
	Total	414	100
Road Insecurity	Frequent	365	88.16
	Not frequent	49	11.84
	Total	414	100

Table 10 reveals that these bandits' disruptions occur frequently. Regular village attacks were reported by 74.2%, seasonal surges in violence by 92.02%, and constant threats to farming cycles by 78.74%. Reoccurring school closures (83.33%) and frequent road insecurity (88.16%) confirm the persistent nature of insecurity in the region.

Table 11: Effects of Armed Banditry on Families Displaced

What are the effects of armed banditry on Families displaced	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Loss of Homes and Livelihoods	Homes and Livelihoods are lost	305	73.7
	Homes and Livelihoods are not lost	109	26.3
	Total	414	100
Overcrowding in IDP Camps	IDP Camps are overcrowded	405	97.82
	IDP Camps are not overcrowded	9	2.18
	Total	414	100
Family Separation and Breakdown	Families are separated	398	96.13
	Families are not separated	16	3.87
	Total	414	100
Vulnerability to Disease and Malnutrition	Disease and Malnutrition are increased	386	93.24
	Disease and Malnutrition are not increased	28	6.76
	Total	414	100
Psychological Trauma and Social Instability	Psychological Trauma and Social Instability are increased	309	74.63
	Psychological Trauma and Social Instability are not increased	105	25.37
	Total	414	100

Table 11 shows that families experience severe disruptions when displaced by bandits. A substantial 73.7% of respondents reported loss of homes and livelihoods, while 97.82% indicated that IDP camps were overcrowded. Family separation was also widespread (96.13%), exposing vulnerable groups to heightened risks. The majority

Table 12: Effects of Armed Banditry on Children's Education

What are the effects of armed banditry on Children's education	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
School closures	Frequent	317	76.5
	Not frequent	97	23.5
	Total	414	100
Displacement and relocation	Always displaced and relocated	410	99.03
	Not displaced and relocated	4	0.97
	Total	414	100
Fear and trauma	Are Afraid and traumatized	378	91.30
	Are not afraid and traumatized	36	8.7
	Total	414	100
Vulnerability	Are vulnerable	357	86.23
	Are not vulnerable	57	13.77
	Total	414	100
Teachers and Learning Materials	Teachers and Learning Materials are lost	397	95.89
	Teachers and Learning Materials not lost	17	4.11
	Total	414	100
Child Labor and Early Marriage	Increased	400	96.62
	Decreased	14	3.38
	Total	414	100

Table 12 highlights the significant impact on children's education. Frequent school closures were reported by 76.5%, while 99.03% indicated that displacement and relocation disrupted schooling. Fear and trauma affected 91.30% of children, and 86.23% were considered highly vulnerable. Loss of teachers and learning materials was also common (95.89%). Alarmingly, 96.62% observed an increase in child labour and early marriage, reflecting deepening social and economic strain.

Table 13: Effects of Armed Banditry on Healthcare Services

Effects of Armed Banditry on Healthcare Services	Responses	n	%
---	------------------	----------	----------

Destruction and Closure of Health Facilities destroyed/closed 283 68.4
ISSN: 2971-7760, Vol: 3, Number: 3, Date: 05/01/2026

Displacement of Health Workers	Facilities not affected	131	31.6
	Total	414	100
	Workers displaced	365	88.2
Restricted Access to Medical Care	Workers not displaced	49	11.8
	Total	414	100
	Access restricted	366	88.4
Interruption of Immunization and Disease Control Programs	Access not restricted	48	11.6
	Total	414	100
	Programs interrupted	301	72.7
Increased Pressure on Urban Health Systems	Programs not interrupted	113	27.3
	Total	414	100
	Pressure increased	401	96.9
Displacement of Health Workers	No increased pressure	13	3.1
	Total	414	100
	Workers displaced	365	88.2

Table 13 outlines the effects on healthcare services. Destruction or closure of health facilities affected 68.4%, while 88.2% noted displacement of health workers, reducing service capacity. Restricted access to medical care was reported by 88.4%, and 72.7% confirmed interruptions in immunization and disease-control programmes. Increased pressure on urban health systems was overwhelming (96.9%), showing a spill-over of rural insecurity into city centres.

Table 14: Effects of Armed Banditry on Psychological Distress

Psychological Distress	Responses	n	Percentage (%)
Chronic Fear and Anxiety	Experienced	358	86.47
	Not experienced	56	13.53
	Total	414	100
Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)	Experienced	386	93.23
	Not experienced	28	6.77
	Total	414	100
Depression and Hopelessness	Experienced	402	97.10
	Not experienced	12	2.90
	Total	414	100
Trauma in Children and Youth	Experienced	395	95.41
	Not experienced	19	4.59
	Total	414	100
Breakdown of Social Trust	Experienced	356	85.99

Table 14 presents psychological consequences. Chronic fear and anxiety affected 86.47%, while PTSD symptoms were reported by 93.23%. Depression and hopelessness were extremely high (97.10%), alongside significant trauma among children (95.41%) and a breakdown of social trust (85.99%). These results illustrate the profound mental health burden associated with ongoing insecurity.

Table 15: Government Military Intervention and its Impact on Banditry

Government's Military Interventions	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Deployment of Joint Task Forces	Implemented	412	99.52
	Not implemented	2	0.48
	Total	414	100
Aerial Bombardments and Ground Raids	Conducted	246	59.42
	Not conducted	168	40.58
	Total	414	100
Establishment of Forward Operating Bases (FOBs)	Established	388	93.71
	Not established	26	6.29
	Total	414	100
Mixed Community Reactions	Present	401	96.86
	Not present	13	3.14
	Total	414	100
Short-Term Gains, Long-Term Challenges	Reported	403	97.34
	Not reported	11	2.66
	Total	414	100
Conducting Operations	Conducted	382	92.27
	Not conducted	32	7.73
	Total	414	100
Establishing Checkpoints	Established	387	93.48
	Not established	27	6.52
	Total	414	100
Intelligence Gathering	Conducted	374	90.33
	Not conducted	40	9.67
	Total	414	100

Table 15 shows that government and military interventions are widely acknowledged. Almost all respondents (99.52%) confirmed the deployment of Joint Task Forces, while 93.71% indicated the establishment of Forward Operating Bases. Intelligence-gathering efforts (90.33%) and checkpoints (93.48%) were also widely recognized. Although aerial bombardments and ground raids were conducted in some areas (59.42%), mixed

Table 5.16: Legislative Measures on Amed Banditry

Legislative Measures Taken	Responses	n	Percentage (%)
Declaration of Banditry as Terrorism	Declared	400	96.61
	Not declared	14	3.39
	Total	414	100
Enactment of Anti-Terrorism and Security Laws	Enacted	398	96.14
	Not enacted	16	3.86
	Total	414	100
Legal Support for Community Policing	Provided	401	96.86
	Not provided	13	3.14
	Total	414	100
Creation of Special Task Forces and Committees	Created	397	95.80
	Not created	17	4.20
	Total	414	100
Approval of Increased Security Budgets	Approved	386	93.24
	Not approved	28	6.76
	Total	414	100

Table 16 highlights strong legislative measures. A large proportion (96.61%) confirmed that banditry has been legally declared terrorism, and 96.14% reported enactment of security laws. Legal support for community policing (96.86%) and the creation of task forces (95.80%) were also widely noted. Increased security budgets were approved by 93.24% of respondents.

Table 17: Effectiveness of Legislative Measures

Effects of Legislative Measures Taken	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Criminalization of Banditry	Implemented	220	53.20
	Not implemented	194	46.80
	Total	414	100
Support for Military Operations	Provided	245	59.18
	Not provided	169	40.82
	Total	414	100
Creation of Special Courts	Created	299	72.22
	Not created	115	27.78
	Total	414	100
Strengthening of Arms Control Laws	Strengthened	250	60.39
	Not strengthened	164	39.61
	Total	414	100

Table 17 assessed the effectiveness of these measures. Criminalization of banditry was implemented according to 59.18%, while 59.18% reported legislative support for military operations. Creation of special courts (72.22%), strengthened arms control laws (60.39%), and enhanced regional security collaboration (62.08%) suggest moderate effectiveness.

Table 18: Actions of Community Leaders

Community Leaders' Actions Taken	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Facilitating Dialogue with Bandits	Taken	373	90.10
	Not taken	41	9.90
	Total	414	100
Coordinating Local Security Efforts	Taken	341	82.37
	Not taken	73	17.63
	Total	414	100
Promoting Unity and Conflict Resolution	Taken	324	78.26
	Not taken	90	21.74
	Total	414	100
Engaging with Authorities and Security Agencies	Taken	298	71.98
	Not taken	116	28.02
	Total	414	100
Raising Awareness and Educating Youth	Taken	308	74.40
	Not taken	106	25.60
	Total	414	100

Table 18 shows that community leaders are actively involved in multiple strategies to address armed banditry. The most frequently reported action is facilitating dialogue with bandits, taken by 90.10% of respondents, indicating that negotiation remains a major conflict-management approach. This is followed by coordinating local security efforts (82.37%), reflecting strong grassroots security mobilization. Additionally, 78.26% noted efforts in promoting unity and conflict resolution, highlighting leaders' roles in strengthening social cohesion. Leaders also engage with government authorities and security agencies (71.98%), showing collaboration between communities and formal security structures. Furthermore, 74.40% reported that leaders focus on raising awareness and educating youth, a preventive measure against involvement in crime.

Table 19: Actions Community Leaders have Taken

Actions Community Leaders Have Taken	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Mediation Efforts	Taken	270	65.21
	Not taken	144	34.79

ISSN: 2971-7760 Vol: 3, Number: 3, Date: 05/01/2026

	Total	414	100
Formation of Community Vigilante Groups	Formed	192	46.38
	Not formed	222	53.62
Total		414	100
	<hr/>		
Establishing Support Networks	Established	106	25.60
	Not established	308	74.40
	Total	414	100
<hr/>			
Liaising with Government and NGOs	Liaised	330	79.71
	Not liaised	84	20.29
	Total	414	100
<hr/>			
Conflict Resolution Mechanisms	Applied	257	62.01
	Not applied	157	37.99
	Total	414	100

Table 19 highlights the various interventions undertaken by community leaders in response to insecurity. The most common action is liaising with government and NGOs, reported by 79.71%, showing strong collaboration with external bodies. Mediation efforts were also widely practiced (65.21%), indicating frequent use of dialogue to resolve tensions. Additionally, 62.01% noted the application of conflict resolution mechanisms, reflecting structured local approaches to peace building. However, only 46.38% reported forming community vigilante groups, suggesting mixed adoption of local security structures. The least common action was establishing support networks (25.60%), indicating limited organized community support systems. Therefore, leaders actively engage in mediation, collaboration, and conflict resolution, with varying levels of involvement in security and support initiatives.

Table 20: Action of the Community Against Armed Banditry

Community-led Actions	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Formation of Vigilante Groups	Formed	229	55.30
	Not formed	185	44.70
	Total	414	100
<hr/>			
Intelligence Sharing with Security Agencies	Shared	85	20.60
	Not shared	329	79.40
	Total	414	100
<hr/>			
Community Dialogues and Mediation	Conducted	77	18.60
	Not conducted	337	81.40
	Total	414	100
<hr/>			
Resettlement and Cooperation Networks	Established	180	43.48
	Not established	234	56.52
	Total	414	100
<hr/>			
Youth Mobilization and Awareness Campaigns	Conducted	23	5.50
	Not conducted	391	94.50
	Total	414	100

Table 20 presents various actions taken by communities in response to armed banditry. The most common action is the formation of vigilante groups, reported by 55.50%, showing reliance on local security structures. Resettlement and cooperation networks were established by 43.48%, reflecting community-driven support systems. However, intelligence sharing with security agencies is relatively low at 20.60%, and community dialogues and mediation are also limited (18.60%), indicating weak collaboration and conflict-resolution efforts. The least practiced action is youth mobilization and awareness campaigns, conducted by only 5.50%, showing minimal youth engagement. Therefore, community efforts focus mainly on self-defense and resettlement, with limited

Table 5.21: Effectiveness of NGO’s Against Armed Banditry

NGOs’ Roles	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Community Engagement and Peace building	Engaged	342	82.60
	Not engaged	72	17.40
	Total	414	100
Early Warning Systems	Provided	378	91.30
	Not provided	36	8.70
	Total	414	100
Victim Support and Rehabilitation	Provided	395	95.41
	Not provided	19	4.59
	Total	414	100
Advocacy and Policy Influence	Engaged	372	89.86
	Not engaged	42	10.14
	Total	414	100
Livelihood and Education Programs	Implemented	388	93.72
	Not implemented	26	6.28
	Total	414	100

Table 21 shows that NGOs play a highly effective role in addressing armed banditry across several key areas. The majority of respondents (95.41%) reported that NGOs provide victim support and rehabilitation, making it the most effective intervention. This is followed by the implementation of livelihood and education programs (93.72%) and the provision of early warning systems (91.30%), indicating strong preventive and supportive measures. Additionally, 89.86% acknowledged NGO involvement in advocacy and policy influence, highlighting their role in shaping security-related policies. Community engagement and peace building efforts were also significant, with 82.60% confirming NGO participation. Overall, NGOs demonstrate high effectiveness in peace building, support services, early warning, advocacy, and livelihood enhancement.

Table 22: Support NGOs Provided

Support NGOs Provided	Responses	n	Percentage (%)
Humanitarian aid (food, shelter, medical aid)	Provided	327	78.99
	Not provided	87	21.01
	Total	414	100
Advocacy and policy influence	Provided	106	25.60
	Not provided	308	74.40

Capacity building and training programs	Total	414	100
	Provided	99	23.91
	Not provided	315	76.09
	Total	414	100
Others	Provided	40	9.66
	Not provided	374	90.34
	Total	414	100

Table 22 outlines the types of support NGOs offered to communities affected by armed banditry. The most common form of assistance is humanitarian aid, such as food, shelter, and medical support, provided to 78.99% of respondents. This indicates that NGOs play a major role in meeting basic survival needs. However, other forms of support are less common. Only 25.60% reported receiving advocacy and policy influence, and 23.91% benefited from capacity-building and training programs, showing limited involvement in long-term empowerment initiatives. The category labeled “Others” was the least reported, at 9.66%. Therefore, NGO support focuses primarily on immediate humanitarian relief, with minimal engagement in training, advocacy, and additional forms of assistance.

Table 23: Effect of Critical Factors on Armed Banditry in Northern Nigeria Region

Most Critical Factors	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Poverty	Critical	340	84.54
	Not critical	62	15.46
	Total	402	100
Unemployment	Critical	167	41.54
	Not critical	235	58.46
	Total	402	100
Weak governance	Critical	161	40.05
	Not critical	241	59.95
	Total	402	100
Inadequate security	Critical	124	30.85
	Not critical	278	69.15
	Total	402	100
Others	Critical	19	4.73
	Not critical	383	95.27
	Total	402	100

Table 23 presents respondents’ views on the most critical factors driving armed banditry in Northern Nigeria. Poverty emerged as the dominant factor, with 84.54% identifying it as critical. This indicates widespread recognition of economic hardship as a major root cause of insecurity. In contrast, unemployment was considered critical by 41.54%, while 40.05% attributed banditry to weak governance. Inadequate security was identified by 30.85%, suggesting that although security lapses contribute to banditry, respondents view socio-economic conditions as more fundamental drivers. Only 4.73% selected other factors, indicating limited emphasis on alternative explanations.

Table 24: Strategies for Addressing Armed Banditry

ISSN: 2971-7760, Vol: 3, Number: 3, Date: 05/01/2026

Strategies for Addressing Armed Banditry	Responses	N	Percentage (%)
Enhanced security measures	Selected	350	86.82
	Not selected	53	13.18
	Total	403	100
Economic support programs	Selected	168	41.69
	Not selected	235	58.31
	Total	403	100
Improved social services	Selected	142	35.24
	Not selected	261	64.76
	Total	403	100
Community engagement and involvement	Selected	150	37.22
	Not selected	253	62.78
	Total	403	100
Others	Selected	16	3.97
	Not selected	387	96.03
	Total	403	100

Table 24 outlines respondents' preferred strategies for addressing armed banditry. Enhanced security measures received overwhelming support (86.82%), reflecting confidence in strengthened policing and military presence. Economic support programmes were selected by 41.69%, highlighting the need to address poverty and livelihood challenges identified in Table 23. Improved social services (35.24%) and community engagement (37.22%) also received notable support, indicating recognition of social development and grassroots involvement as complementary strategies. Only 3.97% selected other approaches, showing strong alignment around mainstream intervention strategies.

[www.https://gmijp-edu.com](https://gmijp-edu.com)

Discussion of the Findings

The discussion section delves into the survey findings regarding the factors driving armed banditry in Northern Nigeria, with specific reference to Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Zamfara State, which are among the worst hit by incessant banditry activities. By analyzing the socio-economic and governance-related issues identified in these three LGAs, this section aims to provide a deeper understanding of the underlying causes of banditry and the responses that have been deemed effective. The discussion also draws comparisons with existing literature to contextualize the findings within the broader scope of research on criminal activities and intervention strategies. This approach not only highlights the consistency of the survey results with previous studies but also identifies areas where further research and policy adjustments may be necessary. Through this discussion, we aim to offer actionable insights that can inform more effective measures to combat banditry and enhance security and socio-economic stability particularly in Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe LGAs of Zamfara State.

The gender distribution, where males constitute 62% and females 38% of respondents, aligns with findings from previous studies on gender participation in surveys conducted in similar socio-cultural contexts. For instance, research by (Omoniyi et al., 2023) highlights male dominance in survey responses due to socio-cultural norms that prioritize men in public and economic activities. In Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe, this pattern reflects the realities of rural northern communities, where men are often more available for surveys due to mobility patterns,

engagement in farming and mining, or responsibilities related to community security. This gender disparity may also reflect differential exposure to banditry, where men are more frequently targeted during farm raids or communal clashes.

Further, the age distribution shows a predominantly youthful respondent base, with 75% of respondents under 40 years old, consistent with demographic trends observed in Northwestern Nigeria (Gwanshak & Hyeladi, 2019). In Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe, this youth dominance is particularly relevant because these LGAs host large numbers of unemployed young people who are either victims of banditry or vulnerable to recruitment due to economic hardship. This youthful demographic has important implications for policy-making, especially in education, employment, and security, highlighting the need for targeted interventions for the young population who bear both the brunt and the consequences of insecurity.

The educational attainment data reveals that a significant portion of respondents have completed secondary education, while a quarter have attained tertiary education. This is consistent with Uwaifo (2022), who noted rising educational attainment in Nigeria. In the context of Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe, the educational profiles underscore both progress and persistent gaps. While secondary school attendance is improving, many communities frequently experience school closures due to bandit attacks, especially in Zurmi and Tsafe. The 10% with no formal education reflects the long-term educational setbacks caused by fear of attacks, displacement, and destroyed school infrastructure.

Regarding occupations, the present study highlights the prominence of farming and trading activities, with half of respondents engaged in farming and one-fifth in trading. These results mirror Olanrewaju (2019), who documented the agricultural dependence of Northwestern Nigeria. In Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe, agriculture especially maize, sorghum, and livestock production has been heavily disrupted by banditry. Farming communities in Maru and Zurmi, in particular, have suffered repeated farm incursions, cattle rustling, and forced displacement. These realities emphasize the need for policies that support agricultural resilience in severely affected LGAs.

The geographical distribution indicates a balanced representation from the various regions within Northwestern Nigeria; however, in this study, specific focus is on Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe, all of which serve as epicentres of banditry in Zamfara State. Their inclusion is crucial for understanding the conflict's localized dynamics. Maru and Zurmi have large forest reserves used as hideouts by armed groups, while Tsafe serves as a key transit corridor for bandits moving between Zamfara, Katsina, and Kaduna states (Adam, 2022). Understanding these unique geographical characteristics is essential for contextualizing the prevalence and persistence of banditry in these LGAs.

The survey findings on gender, age, education, occupation, and geographical distribution in Northwestern Nigeria when applied to Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe provide valuable insights into the socio-economic dynamics of communities most affected by banditry. These results underscore ongoing trends and highlight areas requiring targeted policy interventions to address demographic, educational, and economic challenges aggravated by insecurity in these LGAs.

The survey findings relate closely to several leadership theories. The male dominance in responses underscores the need for transformational leadership to promote gender equity in community participation, especially in Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe, where women and girls are disproportionately affected by village raids and abductions. The youthful respondent base aligns with situational leadership, as leaders must adapt strategies that address

youth unemployment and vulnerability. Servant leadership is relevant to enhancing educational access in like Tsafe and Zurmi, where school disruptions are frequent. Adaptive leadership is crucial for supporting agriculture-dependent households in farming communities across Maru and Zurmi. Contingency leadership emphasizes crafting strategies that reflect each LGA's unique socio-economic dynamics and security risks.

The impact of armed banditry on agricultural activities, as revealed in this study, aligns with previous findings showing severe disruptions (Ojewale et al., 2024). In Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe, farms are routinely abandoned due to fear of attacks, ransom demands, and forced taxation by bandit groups. The moderate and slight impacts reported by some respondents reflect areas where farming continues but under strict limitations or negotiated "access fees" imposed by bandits, especially in parts of Zurmi.

Similarly, the extent to which armed banditry affects daily life is reflected in the 55% of respondents reporting severe disruptions. In Maru, communities such as Dansadau and Mayanchi are frequently under siege, limiting mobility and trade. In Zurmi, persistent attacks have displaced entire villages, while in Tsafe, intermittent highway kidnappings disrupt schooling, commuting, and commercial activities. These findings mirror those of Ojedokun et al. (2024) and Oladoyin et al. (2024).

The impact on household income is profound, especially in Maru and Zurmi, where cattle rustling, destruction of grain stores, extortion, and displacement are prevalent. The 70% reduction in income is consistent with Oladoyin et al. (2024). In Tsafe, roadside banditry and market disruption compound financial hardship, limiting access to basic commodities.

Local market disruptions are similarly severe. Markets such as Magami (Maru LGA) and Kasuwar Daji (Zurmi LGA) have experienced frequent closures due to attacks or threats, affecting food availability and price stability. This mirrors Oladoyin et al. (2024). Banditry-induced price spikes (Adejumo et al., 2024) are particularly visible in Zurmi, where supply chains have collapsed due to road insecurity, and in Tsafe, where traders often avoid high-risk areas, leading to scarcity and inflated prices.

The effects of banditry on family wellbeing are extensive in the three LGAs. With 65% severely affected, family structures are disrupted by displacement, loss of breadwinners, abductions, and trauma (Garba & Kefas, 2024). Children's education is severely affected in Zurmi and Tsafe, where numerous schools remain closed due to attacks, consistent with UNICEF (2020).

Health services are also severely disrupted. In Maru and Zurmi, health workers have been kidnapped or withdrawn, while clinics have closed due to fear of attacks (Nkata & Okpanocha, 2022). Psychological distress is extremely high across all three LGAs, as families live in constant fear, corroborated by (Garry & Checchi, 2020).

These findings reinforce the need for comprehensive interventions addressing socioeconomic and mental health challenges in Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe. Perceptions of government military interventions vary. While 40% see them as highly effective, communities in Maru and Zurmi report that military presence is often insufficient or intermittent, leading to mixed feelings about their impact (Kwede & Danbala, 2024). Legislative measures are moderately appreciated but seen as inadequate without enforcement (Gulbi & Ahmad, 2024).

Community leaders in Tsafe and Maru have adopted proactive measures such as community policing and early warning alerts, consistent with Peter (2022). Community-led actions vigilante groups (Yan Sakai), night patrols,

intelligence sharing are viewed as effective but sometimes lead to retaliation from armed groups. NGO interventions, though present, remain limited due to security risks. Food aid, medical assistance, and temporary shelters have been observed in IDP camps across Tsafe and Zurmi (Spearin, 2001). The critical factors contributing to banditry in these LGAs unemployment, poverty, poor governance, and persistent insecurity are consistent with Amos et al. (2024) and Bello (2022). Youth unemployment is particularly acute in Maru, where many sites that once provided informal jobs are now largely controlled by bandits.

Effective strategies include improved security, youth empowerment, employment opportunities, community engagement, and stronger government policies (Ojo et al., 2023; Onuche & Martins, 2024). Community engagement is especially vital in Tsafe, where local vigilance groups provide early warning systems. To address banditry effectively in Maru, Zurmi, and Tsafe, a multifaceted approach is essential. Enhanced security operations, use of surveillance technology, and improved military presence are fundamental. Youth empowerment through vocational training and job creation will reduce recruitment vulnerability. Community engagement must be strengthened through structured collaboration with security agencies. Government policies must focus on rebuilding social services, restoring education, improving governance, and supporting agricultural recovery. A combination of kinetic and non-kinetic measures, underpinned by strong political will and community participation, is required to ensure long-term stability and security in these three LGAs.

The survey findings on the critical factors contributing to armed banditry in Northern Nigeria and the most effective strategies to address it present a comprehensive overview of the socio-economic and governance challenges face the region that align with previous research and provide a foundation for developing targeted interventions. The present study identifies unemployment as the most significant factor driving armed banditry, affecting 50% of the population. This correlation between high unemployment rates and increased criminal activities is supported, which emphasizes the desperation that pushes individuals towards banditry as a means of survival. Poverty, impacting 30% of the population, further exacerbates this situation by increasing desperation and criminal behavior.

Poor governance, contributing 10%, reflects issues such as corruption and inefficiency, which hinder effective law enforcement and social services. Insecurity itself, accounting for 10%, perpetuates a cycle of violence and instability, making it challenging to curb banditry.

Similarly, the present study presented a multifaceted approach as the most effective strategy for addressing armed banditry. Improved security is viewed as the most effective measure by 35% of respondents, underscoring the need for robust law enforcement and protection measures. Youth empowerment was cited by 25% of respondents as a critical strategy. This approach involves providing young people with skills, education, and opportunities to divert them from criminal activities. Creating job opportunities, which 20% of respondents see as vital, aims to address unemployment and economic hardship. This strategy is crucial for reducing the allure of banditry. Community engagement, supported by 15% of respondents, involves local involvement in peace building and vigilance activities. Effective government policies, although cited by only 5% of respondents, are essential for creating an enabling environment for all other strategies to succeed. The present study underscores the importance of strong governance and policy frameworks in addressing security challenges and supporting socio-economic development.

Conclusion

The survey findings underscore the importance of addressing socio-economic issues, improving governance, and implementing a multi-faceted approach to combat armed banditry in Northern Nigeria. Strategies involving security enhancements, youth empowerment, job creation, community engagement, and effective government policies are crucial for mitigating the impact of banditry. These insights align with previous research, providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors driving banditry and the measures needed to address it effectively.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, several recommendations are proposed to enhance leadership strategies in addressing armed banditry and its socio-economic impacts:

- i. Policy Reform:** Develop and implement comprehensive and adaptive policies that integrate security measures with socio-economic development initiatives. Policies should address root causes of banditry, such as poverty and unemployment.
- ii. Enhanced Coordination:** Improve coordination among government agencies, local leaders, and security forces to ensure a unified and effective response to armed banditry.
- iii. Community Engagement:** Strengthen community-based approaches that involve local stakeholders in identifying and addressing the issues driving banditry. Empowering communities and engaging constructive advocacy can enhance trust and cooperation.
- iv. Resource Allocation:** Allocate sufficient resources to support anti-banditry operations and socio-economic development programs. Ensure transparent and efficient use of funds.
- v. Capacity Building:** Invest in training and capacity building for leaders and security personnel to enhance their effectiveness in combating armed banditry and supporting affected communities.

References

- Abdulfatai, Y. (2021). Leadership and effective human resource management in organization. *Вестник Российского университета дружбы народов. Серия: Государственное и муниципальное управление*, 8(3), 277-296.
- Abdullahi, A. S., & Mukhtar, J. I. (2022). Armed banditry as a security challenge in Northwestern Nigeria. *African Journal of Sociological and Psychological Studies*, 2(1), 45.
- Abdullahi, M., Bukar, B. K., & Bashir, M. (2022). Human security and socio-economic development challenges amid Covid-19 in Nigeria. *AKSU Journal of Administration and Corporate Governance* (2(4).
- Adam, S. Y. (2022). A history of the Kano Book Market, c. 1920-2020.
- Adejumo, A., Thompson, C., & Basnet, S. (2024). The challenges finnish timber firms might encounter when entering the Nigerian Market.
- Ahmed, A. A. (2024). Youth participation in peacebuilding in Somalia: Challenges and opportunities. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Horseed International University (MJHIU)*, 2(1), 126-151.
- Akindoyin, D. I., & Akuche, C. C. (2023). Analysis of development prospect and security crisis in Nigeria. *Lead City Journal of the Social Sciences (LCJSS)*, 8(2), 1-16.

Amos, L. S., Osisiogu, U. C., & Yusuf, U. A. (2024). Analysis of the factors responsible for banditry in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *POLAC INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HUMANITIES AND SECURITY STUDIES*, Number 3, Date: 05/01/2026

Bello, M. M. (2022). The rise of banditry and its attendant effect in governance and socio-economic relations in Zamfara State. *Polac International Journal of Humanities and Security Studies (PIJHSS)*, 1(1), 1-10.

Carba, M. J., & Kefas, P. K. (2024). Banditry and its implications on the livelihood of small scale famers in Nigeria: a study of Taraba State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Management, Social Sciences, Peace and Conflict Studies*, 7(1), 443 - 464.

Garry, S., & Checchi, F. (2020). Armed conflict and public health: into the 21st century. *Journal of Public Health*, 42(3), e287-e298.

Gulbi, A. S., & Ahmad, U. (2024). Challenges and opportunities in Addressing Armed Banditry in Nigeria's Northwest: Insights from the Field1.

Gwanshak, J. Y., & Hyeladi, A. (2019). Contemporary issues of population census in Nigeria.

Iregbenu, P., & Uzonwanne, M. (2015). Security challenges and implications to national stability. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6.

Ishola, H. S., Salawu Ibrahim, O., & Oyewole, L. E. (2024). Security and its socio-economic effect on Nigeria national integrity. *Polac International Journal of Econs & Mgt Science (PI, 10(1))*.

Kwede, C. I., & Danbala, I. N. (2024). Psychological operations as non-kinetic strategy in countering banditry: Insights from the Nigerian military's approach. *Kashere Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 2(2), 226-232.

Mahmoud, A. T., Adeoye, O., & Johnson, H. (2022). Peace, security and conflict in Africa: Nigeria's new security threats. *Lagos Historical Review*, 22, 220-232.

Nkata, R. A., & Okpanocha, O. S. (2022). From boko haram insurgency to banditry: Exploring the changing nature of insecurity and underdevelopment In Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies (IJIRAS)*, 9(4), 1-10.

Odalonu, B. H. (2022). Worsening insecurity in Nigeria and its implications on governance and national development. *African Journal of Humanities and Contemporary Education Research*, 5(1), 31-49.

Ojedokun, U. A., Oyelade, O. K., Adenugba, A. A., & Akanji, O. O. (2024). Insecurity and counter-banditry strategies of the affected communities in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Safer Communities*, 23(1), 23-34.

Ojewale, O. (2024). Learning on the edge: Impacts of banditry on education and strategic options for resilience in northwest Nigeria. *African Security Review*, 33(2), 210-227.

Ojewale, O., Osasona, T., & Shamsudeen, Y. (2024). Climate change and armed banditry in Northwest Nigeria: A troubled synergy of insecurity. In *Armed Banditry in Nigeria: Evolution, Dynamics, and Trajectories* (pp. 15-42). Springer.

Ojo, J. S. Oyewole' S., and Aina, F. (2023). "Forces of terror: Armed banditry and insecurity in North-west Nigeria," *Democracy and Security*, pp. 1–28, doi: 10.1080/17419166.2023.2164924.

Okwuwada, N. (2023). The modern day consequences, causes, and nature of kidnapping, terrorism, banditry, and violent crime in Nigeria: A comprehensive analysis.

Oladoyin, A. M., Osimen, G. U., Adi, I., & Dada, O. (2024). The rising insecurity in Nigeria: Interrogating the linkage between poverty and banditry. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(5), 11406-11415.

Olanrewaju, P. O. (2019). *Compliance of agricultural practices with organic agriculture standard among nigerian farmers*. Doctoral dissertation.

Omitola, B., Adedire, S., Akinrinde, O. O., Omodunbi, O., & Sackflame, M. M. (2021). The triangle of terror: ~~haram, fulani herdsmen, bandits and organised insecurity in Nigeria.~~ *Studia Securitatis*, 15(1), 1.

Ompinji, P. O., Raji, S. O., & Adegoke, O. O. (2023). Influence of religion on domestic violence *The Nigerian Journal of Sociology and Anthropology Vol*, 21(1), 54.

Ouche, O. I., & Martins, E. R. (2024). Banditry and kidnapping in Nigeria: exploring non-traditional approaches to enhance security reliability. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 23(1), 612-619.

Rjoub, H., Ifediora, C. U., Odugbesan, J. A., Iloka, B. C., Xavier Rita, J., Dantas, R. M.,...Martins, J. M. (2021). Implications of governance, natural resources, and security threats on economic development: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(12), 6236.

Spearin, C. (2001). Private security companies and humanitarians: A corporate solution to securing humanitarian spaces? *International Peacekeeping*, 8(1), 20-43.

Ugbomah, N. B., Omede, N., & Philomina, I. O. (2022). Banditry and its threat to human security in Nigeria. *Scholarly Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 1(1), 15-32.

UNICEF. (2020). Global annual results report 2019: goal area 2: every child learns.

Uwaifo, R. O. (2022). Assessment of HIV/AIDS Awareness level among social studies students In Delta North Senatorial District In Delta State. *Delsu Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 19(1), 48-59.

GMIJP, NSUK
[www.https://gmijp-edu.com](https://gmijp-edu.com)